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An Investigation of the Strategic Management Practices of Civil Society Organizations: The Case of Turkey¹

Sivil Toplum Kuruluşlarının Stratejik Yönetim Uygulamalarının İncelenmesi: Türkiye Örneği

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Abstract

In this study, which examines the strategic management practices of Non-Governmental Organizations, the focus is on vision, mission, and principles. In the research, the data of 2023 were taken as the basis. The data obtained from the foundation certificates, establishment documents, private laws, and official websites of the organizations that make up the sample were analyzed by a content analysis method. Analyses show that there are important gaps in strategic management apart from vision and mission statements. The findings obtained in this study; It can be a guide in the context of strategic management for non-governmental organizations that are trying to answer questions from different quarters and want to eliminate doubts, need a more transparent and accountable structure, and are also going through a rapid change and transformation process. However, non-governmental organizations that have not yet adopted the strategic management approach and have not put it on their agenda are also expected to benefit from the results of the research.

Keywords: Non-Governmental Organizations, Humanitarian Aid Organizations, Foundations and Associations, Strategic Management, Mission and Vision.

Özet

S Sivil Toplum Kuruluşlarının stratejik yönetim uygulamalarının incelendiği bu çalışmada vizyon, misyon ve ilkeler üzerinde durulmaktadır. Araştırmada 2023 yılı verileri esas alınmıştır. Örneklemi oluşturan kuruluşların vakıf senedi, kuruluş belgeleri, özel kanunları ve resmi internet sitelerinden elde edilen veriler içerik analizi yöntemiyle incelenmiştir. Analizler stratejik yönetimde vizyon ve

¹ This study is an extended version of the paper presented at the 6th International Congress of Social Sciences held in Hungary in 2021."

misyon ifadeleri dışında önemli boşluklar olduğunu göstermektedir. Bu çalışmada elde edilen bulgular; Farklı çevrelerden gelen soruları yanıtlamaya çalışan, şüpheleri ortadan kaldırmak isteyen, daha şeffaf ve hesap verebilir bir yapıya ihtiyaç duyan, aynı zamanda hızlı bir değişim ve dönüşüm sürecinden geçen sivil toplum kuruluşları için stratejik yönetim bağlamında yol gösterici olabilir. . Ancak henüz stratejik yönetim anlayışını benimsememiş ve gündemine almamış sivil toplum kuruluşlarının da araştırma sonuçlarından faydalanması beklenmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Sivil Toplum Kuruluşları, İnsani Yardım Kuruluşları, Vakıf ve Dernekler, Stratejik Yönetim, Misyon ve Vizyon

1. Introduction

The organization, which reveals its reason for existence and, accordingly, the ideal place it wants to reach in the future, must also determine the way how it will reach it. This path is also called the strategy of an organization. The word strategy is also used in the sense of "the path taken to achieve the determined goals". In terms of organizations, it is possible to define strategy as "a set of goals, important policies, and plans prepared to achieve the goals". The minimum loss or maximum benefit from the developments in the field of activity of the organizations depends on its strategy. In fact, not only organized structures, but even an ordinary person with a certain purpose: When he thinks about how and in which way he will achieve this goal, he has entered the field of "strategy". Just as in the military field, strategy is used in the sense of "tactics and plans to be applied to win the war", and the way or ways that individuals, institutions and organizations follow to gain "superiority" over their "competitors" in achieving their goals also determine their "strategies". In this direction, when we consider the strategy in terms of the public sector, we can define it as the measures taken in every field and the use of all kinds of tools to achieve the goals that an institution (or the state) chooses in accordance with its policy.

In this sense, strategy is a set of decisions that show how the organization's goals and objectives will be achieved. Strategy with a holistic approach; It can be defined as "the process of determining the goals that will adapt by constantly analyzing the organization and its environment, planning the activities, and rearranging the necessary tools and resources to give direction to the organization and to provide competitive advantage". Mission and vision statements are the most frequently used management techniques by managers worldwide (Bart, 1996). It is stated that there are different reasons why mission and vision statements are a frequently preferred management technique. The first reason is that mission and vision statements explain simple but organizationally important questions (What are we for? What is our purpose? What are we striving to achieve?). On the other hand, mission statements are the beginning of all strategic intentions and activities. Mission statements are also the starting point in projects such as total quality management, restructuring, reengineering, and self-directed working groups (Bart, 1997). Additionally, mission statements

also motivate organizational members in line with organizational goals (Collins & Porras, 1991). Another function of mission and vision statements is to define the framework or boundary in the formation of organizational strategy (Thompson & Strickland, 1992). Ireland and Hitt (1992) suggest that mission and vision statements serve as criteria in resource allocation decisions that can be considered critical for the organization. Emerging concepts such as social responsibility, sustainable growth, and stakeholder interests have caused businesses to change their mission concepts. Business values and philosophy can also lead to a mission change. In short and in a nutshell, all changes that may occur in the reason for the existence of the enterprise constitute a reason for the change in its mission.

Vision, mission, goals and objectives, policy, and strategy are concepts that are closely related to each other. Like the vision, the strategy is linked to the future of the organization. However, while vision is a more abstract statement of the future, strategy has a more concrete feature. After determining the vision and mission, the policy and objectives will guide the strategies. The main lines of the strategy are determined with the vision, and the details are left to the process. Therefore, the vision is deliberately and consciously put forward, while the strategy emerges (Mintzberg, 1993). When evaluated from this viewpoint, First, the vision should be formed, and other processes, including the mission, should be based on the vision. Bart (1996) and Collins and Porras (1996) argue that the strategic management process begins with the writing of the mission statement and the vision will be formed accordingly. Although these discussions still continue, the vision is “Where do we want to go?” answer the question of “What needs to be done?” It seems that a consensus has been reached on the issue (Kılıç, 2010). Based on this idea, if the plan is the road map and the vision is the direction we are going, the mission statement can be compared to the traffic signs on the road. Therefore, while the vision statement directs the organization to future goals or achievements, the mission statement directs the current, critical, and strategic decisions (Drohan, 1999). The process of expressing this strategy is possible with vision and mission statements (Anthony, 2012).

2. Literature

Strategic Management gives an organization's employees a broader perspective and they can better understand how their work fits into the overall organizational plan and how it relates to other organizational members. Employees can understand the reaction of environmental changes on the organization and the possible response of the organization with the help of strategic management. In this way, employees can assess the impact of such changes on their work and confront them effectively. One of the most important roles of strategic management is to fully involve the various functional areas of the organization and to ensure that these functional areas harmonize and come

together. Another role of strategic management is to continually pursue the goals and objectives of the organization. Mission and vision play a crucial role in the strategic management processes of organizations.

2.1. Mission

Every institution/organization has a "reason for existence" whether it is for profit or not. The mission statement, as a different concept from vision, explains the organization's reason for existence. Alter (2000) sees the mission as the heart of social existence. Because the mission is accepted as an important starting point in the strategy formation process. Mission, which reveals what an organization should do, also means "special task undertaken". Mission, it gives direction to employees, partners, and management and sets out the basic objectives and principles. Therefore, it also expresses the strategy that will enable to achieve the goals. Mission: It is a clear and unequivocal expression of what the organization does, why it exists, its ultimate goals, its different aspects from its competitors, and why it should be preferred (Lamba, 2014). Organizations should reveal their differences from other organizations by expressing their missions clearly and unequivocally (Dobson & Starkey, 1998). Additionally, the mission is also important in terms of revealing the differences of the organizations with their competitors, gaining identity and communicating with their customers. Emerging concepts such as social responsibility, sustainable growth, and stakeholder interests have caused businesses to change their mission concepts.

Business values and philosophy can also lead to a mission change. We see that there is no consensus in the definitions of the concept of 'mission' included in the management literature in the 1960s, and the most common emphasis is on the aspect of 'explaining the organization's reason for existence'. If businesses put their mission statements in writing to present them to their internal and external stakeholders, they turn it into a mission statement (Klemm, Sanderson, & Luffman, 1991). In business, the mission should be determined at the point of formation of the idea of establishing the business. Among these features, the most frequently and widely expressed ones are; short, qualitative (Peters & Waterman, 1995), emphasizing the market, product, and customers, and motivating employees (Alkoç, 2010).

2.2. Vision

Vision, which is the most important means of expressing the aims of an organization in line with its reason for existence, is a concrete future image that determines what the institution or organization wants to be in the future. The word vision comes from the Latin word to see and is defined as "the act or power of imagination", "the method of seeing or envisioning" and "unusual intuition or foresight" (Miser, 2006). Kantabutra and Avery (2010) describe vision as the starting

point of an organization's transformation process. According to McGowan and Sykes (2015), a vision statement is the expression of an ideal-desired outcome that inspires and energizes, creates a mental picture of goals. In short, a vision is a picture of what an organization wants to be. Creating a vision provides flexibility in an uncertain environment. Vision is a general guide (Mintzberg & Waters, 1985). Swanson (2010), on the other hand, likens vision to the magnet used by a person looking for a needle in a haystack, and states that vision directs followers and resources just as a magnet attracts a needle. The most important function of the “vision” in the long run, to guide the organization's strategy, goals, and objectives. Therefore, it performs a unifying function between different units, especially in organizations that perform more than one function.

A vision statement defines where the organization wants or intends to be in the future or where it should be to best meet the needs of stakeholders. The vision statement contains a shared understanding of the nature and purpose of the organization and uses this understanding to drive and guide the organization toward a better cause. In performing the task, it describes what the corporate future will look like. The vision should have certain characteristics. Vision alone does not make sense; it should be linked to core values and goals. The vision is original for every manager and leader; It gains value as it is shared and gives direction to strategies.

Factors affecting an organization's vision: the need to control the destiny (future) of the organization, the need for creative strategies, the need to reverse and improve the negative trend, and the need for change in the organizational culture. The vision statement should be clear, clear, understandable, attractive, original, future-defining, inspiring, guiding and written; should include goals, strategies, policies and values. (Collins and Porras, 1999; Hitt, Ireland, and Hoskisson, 2000; Lipton, 1996).

2.3. Importance of Vision and Mission Statements for Strategic Management:

It is impossible to understand the concepts of mission and vision, which are the basic concepts of strategic management process and strategic direction, by simply defining them, by looking at their definitions, and to reveal the ambiguity observed in these concepts. However, although these concepts have been examined in the strategic management process literature, generally accepted definitions have not been found.

Businesses motivate their employees by explaining their mission and vision; they try reaching their goals with appropriate strategies by inspiring them, creating a sense of common sharing and creating synergy. Although 'mission' and 'vision' are important concepts in management science and especially in the strategic management process, there are no generally accepted definitions for these concepts. While many studies in the related literature focus on the concepts of mission and

vision, the place of these concepts in strategic management and their contributions to businesses, very few researchers have discussed the criteria for creating a mission and vision.

While the criteria for creating a mission are generally referred to in the studies, the concept of vision has been left in the background a little more. If businesses put their mission statements in writing to present them to their internal and external stakeholders, they will transform it into a mission statement (Klemm, Sanderson, & Luffman, 1991). Vision is a guide that enables organizations to see the future from today, directs them to the direction they want to go and shows their long-term goals. Organizations that see the future gain competitive advantage against their competitors in the same market and go one step ahead. Global organizations need strong visions (Guzelcik, 1999). Oghojafor et al. (2011) expressed vision and mission statements as starting points in the strategic management process. Mintzberg (1994), on the other hand, states that strategic thinking is only possible with vision, and that there is a close relationship between vision, mission, and strategic planning and strategy. In this context, strategic planning is the process of planning goals, strategies and policies to bring organizations to their future visions (Massod et al., 2012).

In the strategic management literature, the vision and mission statements of the organizations are accepted as the most important steps of strategic orientation. Following these two important steps, a strategic plan is created to realize the vision and mission (Alcorn, 1998). Ten times the time spent and mental, emotional, and physical energy is recovered through a strategic plan (McGowan & Sykes, 2015). Additionally, vision and mission statements are seen as the communication tools of the organization and guide the behavior and decisions of managers and employees. These statements, similarly, communicate the intentions and objectives of the organizations to the stakeholders. For these reasons, vision and mission statements are seen as critical for the success of organizations (Hodes, 2015). In many studies, it has been determined that the vision and mission statements of the organizations have a positive effect on the effectiveness of these organizations (Brătianu & Bălănescu, 2008)

The vision should have certain characteristics (Çetin, 2009; Özer, 2010; Karaman,2005;). Vision alone does not make sense; it should be linked to core values and goals. The vision is original for every manager and leader; It gains value as it is shared and gives direction to strategies. Factors affecting an organization's vision: the need to control the destiny (future) of the organization, the need for creative strategies, the need to reverse and improve the negative trend, and the need for change in the organizational culture. At the stage of determining the vision, the entire burden should not be left only to the senior managers, but also other employees in the enterprises should be ensured to participate in this process. In this way, individuals will be more committed to the vision. This will ensure that employees are more motivated to reach the target set by the enterprise. The

vision statement should be clear, clear, understandable, attractive, original, future-defining, inspiring, guiding and written (Dinler, 2009; Collins & Porras, 1999; Hitt, Ireland and Hoskisson, 2000; Lipton, 1996).

Vision and mission statements act as catalysts that strengthen the actions of organizations (Anthony, 2012). Clearly expressed vision and mission statements motivate individuals and teams in the organization by providing strong communication. For this reason, it is important to express the vision and mission in a way that strengthens the activities of the organizations. For this reason, many studies have been conducted in both international and local literature on what elements an effective vision and mission statement should consist of. In the main studies on vision (James and Porras, 1996; Alcorn, 1998), it is stated that the vision statement consists of core values, core goals, a big goal, and the definition of what will happen if the goal is achieved. Core values express the values of the people working in the organization, and core goals express the reason why individuals become members of the organization. However, some studies on which elements a successful vision should consist of are summarized in Table-1.

Table 1. Components Considered in Vision Studies

Researcher	Vision Components
Collins and Porras (1996)	Core values, core goals, big goals
Alcorn (1998)	Core values, core goals, big goals
Abelman and Amy (2008)	Sharedness, openness, compelling, complexity, advantages, and observability.
Bratianu and Balanescu (2008)	Reason for existence, core values, social responsibility, literariness, meaningfulness
Kasowski and Filion (2010)	Future orientation, market orientation, clarity and feasibility, and change orientation
Burke (2011)	Conciseness, clarity, concreteness and challenge, goals, future orientation, desired goals, and success criteria
Moon and Husbands (2012)	Leadership, innovation, globality, growth-development, leadership, quality, social responsibility, economy
Masood et al. (2012)	Conciseness, clarity, concreteness, creativity, inspiring, self-assured, reassuring, identifying opportunities, future-oriented, action-oriented, long-term, and flexibility
Haghighi et al. (2013)	Conciseness, clarity and clarity, future-oriented, change-oriented, inspiring, ambitious, and clear goals
Papulova (2014)	Understandability, memorability, positivity, motivating, inspiring, captivating, challenging, future-oriented

In studies on mission characteristics, it is stated that a mission statement should answer three questions in general. What are we doing? How do we do it? Who are we doing it for? are questions. The studies on which elements a successful mission statement should consist of are summarized in the table below.

Table 2. Componentes Considered in Mission Studies

Researcher	Mission Components
Bart and Baetz (1998)	Vision, organizational goals, values, capabilities, competitive position, competitive strategy, specific standards of behavior, general objectives, clear and guiding goals, non-financial goals, reason for existence, job description, customer/market
Drohan (1999)	Actions, core values, guiding principles, and priorities
Bratianu and Balanescu (2008)	Reason for existence, core values, social responsibility, legitimacy, meaningfulness
Kasowski and Jacques, (2010)	Future orientation, market orientation, clarity and feasibility, and change orientation
Papulova (2014)	Company philosophy, customer, product/service, place/markets, continuity/growth/profitability, employee, talent orientation, and image orientation

3. Methods

In this study, which used a qualitative research design, the document analysis method was preferred. Document analysis is a qualitative research method used to analyze the content of written documents meticulously and systematically (Wach, 2013). The sample of this study consisted of 29 leading NGOs based in Turkey and legally granted special status by the Turkish government. To ensure the validity and reliability of the research; first, the collected data were presented directly with a descriptive approach, without interpretation or evaluation. To ensure the external validity of the research, the method of the research was defined in detail. Additionally, “expert review” and “confirmation review” strategies were used. In this context, evaluation meetings were held with experts who had worked in the relevant field, and arrangements were made with the feedback received regarding the overall research process and the suitability of the raw data.

4. Findings

In Turkey, associations, trade unions, political parties, professional organizations, and foundations that are public institutions are defined as non-governmental organizations. Unions and professional

organizations in public institutions provide services for the interests of their members, while foundations are organized with transferred tangible assets to ensure the continuity of service. It is difficult to evaluate the political parties, whose main purpose is to gain a place in the political society, as non-governmental organizations in the classical sense. However, political parties in the opposition have aspects that overlap with the aims of civil society in terms of their interest in social problems and their function of controlling the current government. Associations are the highest in number among non-governmental organizations in Turkey. Table 3 shows the distribution of associations operating in Turkey according to their fields of activity.

Table 3. Analysis of associations in terms of their fields of activity

Vocational and Solidarity Associations	38346
Religious Associations	17,964
Sports Associations	7403
Educational Research Societies	6,228
Culture, Art, and Tourism Associations	5,935
Humanitarian Associations	5,93
Associations to Maintain Social Values	2,744
Environmental, Natural Life, and Animals Protection Associations	2,709
Associations Active in the Field Of Health	2,685
Individual Teaching and Social Development Associations	2,523
Reconstruction, Urbanization, and Development Associations	1,58
Rights and Advocacy Associations	1,526
Associations for the Disabled	1,303
Thought Associations	1,035
Associations Supporting Public Institutions and Staff	922
Food, Agricultural, and Livestock Associations	843
Societies of Solidarity with Diaspora Turks	746
International Organizations and Cooperation Associations	562
Relatives Of Martyrs and Veterans Associations	497
Associations for the Old and Children	304
Associations Related to Children	14
Unknown	2
Total	49691

Source: <https://www.siviltoplum.gov.tr/derneklerin-faaliyet-alanlarina-gore-dagilimi> (Access Date 05.02.2023) Turkiye Ministry of Interior General Directorate of Civil Society Relations

The General Directorate of Civil Society Relations of the Ministry of Interior is responsible for the establishment and supervision of associations in Turkey. Table 4 shows the number of active and closed associations in Turkey.

Table 4. The number of active and closed associations in Turkey.

Number of Active Associations	101,801
Number of Closed Associations	208.063
Total Number of Associations	309,864

Source: <https://www.siviltoplum.gov.tr/dernek-sayilari> (Access Date 05.02.2023)

The fields of activity of the associations within the scope of the study were examined. The results of the examination are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Fields of activity of associations

Field of Area	f	%
Education	16	27,5
Culture	12	20,6
Humane aid	9	15,5
Health	6	10,3
Service to Youth	6	10,3
Protecting Children	2	3,42
Professional Solidarity/Professional Studies	3	5,17
Emergencies/Disaster	2	3,42
Art	1	1,72
Environment	1	1,72

Table 6 shows the analysis results of the non-governmental organizations within the scope of the research in terms of the field of activity, mission, vision, goals and objectives, working principles/values/principles, social responsibility, and ethical values. In this context, non-governmental organizations received a standard score determined for each area, and a total score was produced.

Table 6. Analysis of associations in terms of mission, vision, goals, and objectives and principles according to their fields of activity

NGO	Field of Activity	Mission	Vision	Goals and Objectives	Working Principles / Values/ Principles	Score
n1	Services and Health for the Disabled	✓	✓	✓	-	75
n2	Art and culture	-	-	✓	-	25
n3	Professional Work	-	-	✓	-	25
n4	Environmental Protection	✓	✓	✓	✓	100
n5	Child welfare	✓	✓	✓	-	75
n6	Health	✓	✓	✓	✓	100
n7	Health and Education	✓	-	✓	✓	75
n8	Health	✓	✓	✓	-	75
n9	Humane aid	✓	✓	✓	✓	100
n10	Humanitarian Aid/Education and Culture	✓	✓	✓	-	75
n11	Humanitarian Aid/Health/ Education and Culture/ Emergencies/ Disaster	✓	✓	✓	✓	100
n12	Education	✓	✓	✓	✓	100
n13	Education	✓	✓	✓	✓	100
n14	Professional Solidarity/	-	-	✓	✓	50
n15	Humane aid	✓	✓	✓	✓	100
n16	Education	✓	-	✓	✓	75

n17	Emergencies/Disaster/Humanitarian Aid	✓	✓	✓	✓	75
n18	Health and Child Protection	✓	✓	✓	✓	100
n19	Health	✓	✓	✓	✓	100
n20	Humane aid	✓	✓	✓	✓	100
n21	Education and Culture	✓	✓	-	-	50
n22	Humanitarian Aid/Education and Culture	✓	✓	✓	✓	100
n23	Humanitarian Aid/Education and Culture	✓	✓	✓	-	75
n24	Education and Culture/ Service to Youth	✓	✓	✓	-	75
n25	Education and Culture/ Service to Youth	✓	✓	✓	✓	100
n26	Education and Culture/ Service to Youth	✓	✓	✓	-	75
n27	Education and Culture/ Service to Youth	✓	✓	✓	-	75
n28	Education and Culture/ Youth Service/ Humanitarian Aid	✓	✓	✓	-	75
n29	Education and Culture/ Service to Youth	-	-	✓	-	25
						78,44

According to the results of the content analysis on the data set;

- Organizations operating in the field of culture/art, professional solidarity/work do not have vision and mission statements,
- The lowest score received by organizations operating in the field of professional solidarity/professional study,
- Generally, organizations reporting that they operate in a single field receive high scores,
- 25 organizations have Mission statements and 23 organizations have Vision statements,
- 28 organizations made statements regarding the aims/targets,
- 16 organizations include statements about working Principles/values/principles,
- 3 companies carried out institutional change studies in line with the strategic management approach,
- It was found that 4 of the 29 organizations examined directly emphasized ethical values, and only two of them explained the ethical values of the organization.

The mission, vision, aims and goals, working principles/values/principles of the associations, which are the sample of this study, were examined. The results of the analysis are shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Presence of associations' mission, vision, goals, and objectives and principles

Statements	f	%
Mission	25	86,2
Vision	23	79,3
Goals and Objectives	28	96,5
Working Principles/ Values/ Principles	16	55,1

Because of the content analysis of the mission statements of the 29 associations that make up the sample, 10 mission statement components emerged. Table 8 shows the results of the analysis of the mission statements of the associations in terms of 10 components.

Table 8. Mission Statement Components Used in Content Analysis:

	Beneficiaries	Products/Services	Location/Markets	Technology	Continuity, Growth and Profitability	Philosophy	Competence	Public Concern	Employees	Communication	Total
n1	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	-	70
n2	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	-	✓	✓	-	✓	70
n3	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	-	-	70
n4	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	-	80
n5	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	-	70
n6	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	-	80
n7	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	80
n8	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	90
n9	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	-	80
n10	✓	✓	✓	-	-	✓	-	✓	-	-	50
n11	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	90
n12	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	-	✓	-	-	60
n13	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	-	✓	-	-	60
n14	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	80
n15	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	80
n16	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	80
n17	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	-	✓	-	✓	70
n18	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	100
n19	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	-	✓	-	-	60
n20	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	80
n21	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	-	70
n22	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	80

n23	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	-	80
n24	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	80
n25	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	-	70
n26	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	80
n27	✓	✓	✓	-	-	-	-	✓	-	-	40
n28	✓	✓	✓	-	-	✓	-	✓	-	-	50
n29	✓	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	10
Total	290	280	280	70	250	250	210	280	50	100	2060

Because of the content analysis of the mission statements of the 29 associations that make up the sample, 9 vision statement components emerged. Table 9 shows the results of the analysis of the mission statements of the associations in terms of 9 components.

Table 9. Vision Statement Components Used in Content Analysis

	Idealist	Originality	Distinctiveness	Attractiveness	Brevity	Inspiring	Future Descriptor	Social Responsibility	Ethic	Total
n1	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	80
n2	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	-	70
n3	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	80
n4	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	90
n5	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	90
n6	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	80
n7	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	90
n8	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	80
n9	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	90
n10	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	-	70
n11	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	90
n12	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	90

n13	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	90
n14	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	90
n15	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	90
n16	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	90
n17	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	90
n18	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	90
n19	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	80
n20	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	80
n21	✓	✓	✓	-	-	✓	✓	✓	-	60
n22	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	80
n23	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	90
n24	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	90
n25	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	90
n26	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	-	✓	-	60
n27	✓	-	-	-	-	✓	-	✓	-	30
n28	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	-	60
n29	✓	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	10
Total	290	270	260	220	250	280	240	280	180	2270

5. Conclusion and Suggestions

The "Mission statement" of 25 associations, the "Vision statement" of 23 organizations, and the "goals/targets" of 28 organizations show that there is an awareness in terms of strategic management. In this study on non-profit organizations, remarkable findings that are thought to be valuable in the policy-making process were obtained. These associations, which should be highly trusted by the public and financed largely by donations, should focus on transparency and accountability. Ethical and social responsibility principles can play a leading role in this process. However, it was found that 4 of the 29 organizations examined directly emphasized ethical values, and only two of them explained the ethical values of the organization. Unfortunately, it has been observed that the examined associations do not attach importance to the strategic management components, especially the mission and vision statements. Vision and mission statements explain an institution's political stance, vision for the future, and reason for existence. The organization defines and expresses itself through its vision and mission. However, associations in the fields of culture/art and professional solidarity/work do not have vision and mission statements. On the other hand, the situation in professional ethics, which is an important branch of business ethics, does not

seem very encouraging. In this respect, it was seen that "professional solidarity/professional work" associations got the lowest score. Additionally, it has been observed that only 3 organizations have mentioned the "institutional change" studies, which have an important place in strategic management.

The fact that associations operate in more than one field may have been effective in the formation of this undesirable picture. Because, it is seen that organizations that report that they operate in a single field are more successful in strategic management processes. In this respect, the diversity in the field of activity seems to have caused clutter and lack of focus in the context of strategic management. As a suggestion, it can be suggested that associations determine one field of activity and insist on this issue. Moreover highlighted the 16 associations' statements about "Working Principles/values/principles". This finding shows that there is a need for more focus and care in the above-mentioned issues such as principled attitude, transparency, accountability, ethics, and social responsibility.

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